

SELF-REGULATED LEARNING PROMOTION AND TEACHING PRACTICES OF SHS TEACHERS ON THE STUDY SKILLS OF SHS STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 8

Pages: 831-839

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2708

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14413315

Manuscript Accepted: 11-16-2024

Self-Regulated Learning Promotion and Teaching Practices of SHS Teachers on the Study Skills of SHS Students

Phoebe P. Escosar,* Louie Jay R. Caloc
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the influence of self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of students. There is an affirmation that self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers predict the study skills of students. This study was carried out through a quantitative research design, employing the descriptive-correlational method. A simple random sampling was utilized to determine the number of samples and survey questionnaires were used to gather the data. Likewise, mean and standard deviation, Pearson (r), and regression analysis were the statistical tools utilized to answer the research objectives. Findings revealed that the level of self-regulated learning promotion and study skills of students were highly prevalent which means that they are always manifested, while the level of teaching practices of SHS teachers is high which conveys that the variable is frequently manifested. Nonetheless, a significant relationship exists between the variables under investigation. Thus, this connects to the idea that one's self-regulated learning and teaching practices influence study skills.

Keywords: *self-regulated learning, teaching practices, study skills, senior high school students*

Introduction

Study skills refer to a student's proficiency in obtaining, documenting, and applying information and ideas (Gögüş & Ertek, 2020). In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted the education sector. In accordance with Maican and Cocoradă (2021), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) statistics in June revealed that despite the easing of lockdown measures in many countries, almost 55.2% of learners, equivalent to nearly a billion worldwide, were still affected by the pandemic across all education levels, with schools and higher education institutions remaining closed in 119 countries. As stated by Salcedo-Relucio (2019), Senior High School students (SHS) do not practice habitual study which leads to low grades in school. Additionally, the pandemic has disrupted traditional classroom learning routines, impacting students' study habits and time management in terms of their academic engagement (Garcia et al., 2020).

Study habits tell a person how much he will learn, how far he wants to go, and how much he wants to earn (Bibi et al., 2020). This means that study habits are crucial to students' academic performance. As explicated by Gettinger and Seibert (2019), study skills are fundamental to academic competence. Furthermore, academic proficiency is linked to the understanding and use of efficient study techniques. The reason why capable students at all grade levels may struggle in school is not because they lack talent, but because they lack effective study techniques. Training students to become effective self-regulated learners is very important (Baars & Wijnia, 2018). All these contribute to a life-long learning atmosphere, which determines how adaptable and successful the society is being transformed everyday.

There have been numerous studies about the study skills of students, however, no study has yet presented three variables on this matter. Additionally, most of these studies are conducted in other locations, with none focusing on study skills here in Davao City. Most studies on study skills are done in different places. By focusing on these three variables which are the self-regulated learning promotion (Jansen et al., 2019), teaching practices (Segolsson & Hirsh, 2019), and study skills (Gögüş & Ertek, 2020), this research strives to provide a more nuanced understanding of study skills, tailored to the specific needs of students in Davao City. This study goes beyond a mere examination of teaching practices; and explores the promotion of self-regulated learning as a central aspect. The findings are anticipated to offer practical implications for educators, providing valuable guidance on how to optimize teaching approaches to not only enhance study skills but also instill lifelong learning habits among SHS students.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of students. More explicitly, the study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of self-regulated learning promotion;
2. To describe the level of teaching practices of shs teachers;
3. To assess the level of the study skills of the students;
4. To determine the relationship between:
 - 4.1. self-regulated learning promotion and study skills; and
 - 4.2. teaching practices of SHS teachers and study skills.
5. To test the influence of self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of students.

Literature Review

Self-Regulated Learning Promotion

In accordance with Zimmerman and Schunk (2011), they describe SRL as an active and ongoing process in which learners proactively engage their thoughts, emotions, and actions in a systematic manner to achieve their individual goals as cited by Theobald (2021). In line with Pandey et al. (2018), they define self-regulation as a psychological concept that includes various crucial skills, such as managing emotions, maintaining positive relationships, avoiding inappropriate or aggressive behaviors, and being capable of independent learning. According to Tosuncuoğlu (2019), when a learner exercises self-regulation, they identify their requirements, set goals, research appropriate learning materials, and evaluate their own learning experiences.

Self-regulated learning means that students learn by themselves, using their thoughts and actions to reach their learning goals. They take charge of their learning, set goals, keep track of their progress, and adjust their strategies as needed to do better in school. A substantial body of research in education has demonstrated the positive effects of self-regulated learning on student motivation and has come to the conclusion that self-regulation plays a fundamental role in the variations in student accomplishment (Vosniadou, 2020). Positive effects include students reporting slightly higher levels of self-confidence, pre-lecture review, and comfort in asking for help from instructors after attending the self-regulation session. Students report using goal-setting behaviors less frequently, seeing minimal increases in their ability to avoid distractions when studying, and using rephrasing to rehearse important course concepts (Maleki et al., 2018).

Teaching Practices

Teaching practices are ways through which students are motivated to engage in knowledge development, based on their unique abilities (Segolsson & Hirsh, 2019). The process of teaching and learning can be described as a transformation of knowledge from instructors to learners (Munna & Kalam, 2021). It encompasses multiple components, where an educator sets learning goals, creates educational materials, and demonstrates a teaching and learning approach. According to Peterson et al. (2018), pedagogy is at the heart of teaching and learning. Pedagogy offers structures for the multitude of decisions educators must make regarding their methods of instruction. Pedagogical innovation, like any other type of innovation, uses existing ideas, tools, or practices and combines them in new ways to solve difficulties when current practice is insufficiently satisfying needs. According to Malgapo and Ancheta (2020), educators often use similar pedagogical methods and strategies, yet some are more effective and suitable than others.

In broad terms, pedagogical competencies have typically been seen as either a model of potential behaviors and abilities that enable effective performance in an activity or as a minimal professional requirement, often legally defined, that professionals are expected to attain (Suciu & MĂȚĂ, 2011). In the study of Palbusa (2021), it was recommended that encouraging the development of critical pedagogy is suggested as a means to empower learners as active agents of social change. This recommendation implies that educators should serve as catalysts for curriculum reforms, aiming not only to make learning relevant but also to foster liberation and, consequently, humanization. Moreover, Santos et al. (2019) concluded that implementing innovative pedagogical methods fosters increased student engagement, enhances critical and creative thinking skills, diminishes apathy, and actively participates in their learning experience.

Study Skills

Study skills refer to a student's proficiency and obtaining, documenting, and applying information and ideas (Göğüş & Ertek, 2020). Study skills include many tasks and psychological variables, such as time management, students' information processing skills, setting appropriate goals, selecting an appropriate study environment, applying suitable note-taking strategies, concentrating, selecting principal ideas, self-testing, organization, and managing anxiety. Understanding of research study abilities, understanding of private understanding designs together and the application of suitable approaches can dramatically affect students' success. By being mindful of efficient research study strategies together with customizing techniques to suit varied understanding designs, students can improve their academic efficiency and total success. This recognition equips students to take on approaches that reverberate with their unique choices advertising a much more tailored along efficient understanding.

According to Belbase et al. (2018), many components add to the high quality of student understanding including the residence atmosphere the student setup, and also the class environment. In addition, both instructor-related and also student-specific elements play essential functions together with the impact of educational products matched with the web content covered in the training course. Additionally, the harmony of these varied variables collectively forms the instructional experience stressing the manifold nature of what figures out the efficiency plus high quality of student understanding.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researchers used quantitative design employing the descriptive-correlational approach because its goal was to measure the characteristics described in the research questions and to investigate the connections between the variables included (Saunders et al., 2019). To be specific, the goal was to find more about the correlation between the dependent variable which is study skills, and the

independent variables which are self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices. As stated by Mertler (2018), understanding the nature and strength of the relationship between these variables can help predict future conditions or behaviors in one variable from what is presently known of another variable by employing a predictive correlational design. Therefore, significant justification from renowned authors sheds light on the researchers' conclusion that the combination of descriptive and correlational design is most appropriate composition to address research objectives regarding the level and relationship between self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills of students.

Respondents

According to Patino and Ferreira (2018), inclusion criteria are defined as critical characteristics of the target population that the researchers/investigators must employ to answer their research questions. On this note, the selection of the study's respondents was primarily based on the inclusion criteria which are: within the age range of eighteen to thirty years old, either male or female, experienced, and knowledgeable about the research topic or phenomenon of interest. The exclusion and withdrawal criteria for the selection of respondents were observed as well based on the following: First, if the senior high school student is not enrolled in the current semester. Second, if the student does not belong to the aforementioned strand. Third, if the student does not have the background knowledge or any experience related to the topic under investigation. Lastly, if the student is under the influence of an alcoholic drink because it might affect the answers of the researchers.

Prior to examining the type of sampling method to use in the study, it is essential to understand what sampling entails and why researchers might choose a sample. Sampling is selecting a subset from a sampling frame or the entire population. It can be used to make inferences about a population or generalizations about a theory. In essence, it depends on the choice of sample technique to be used (Taherdoost, 2016). In this case, the researcher utilized simple random sampling, which means that every individual in the population, as long as qualified based on the inclusion criteria, had an equal opportunity to be selected and included in the sample.

In terms of determining the sample size, Burmiester and Aitken (2012) stated that the sample size is one aspect of research design that investigators must consider as they organize their study. The reasons to calculate the required sample size precisely include acquiring statistically significant results and guaranteeing that research resources are used efficiently and ethically. To get the number of samples, the study used the Raosoft formula which resulted in 110 respondents who were senior high school students under the GAS strand. To justify the selection of a particular strand, the researcher based this on the previous studies since the variables under investigation are general in nature.

The current study consists of three parameters (one dependent variable and two independent variables). Moreover, Biau (2008) stated that the advantages of a large sample size for interpreting significant results are that it permits a more exact estimation of the treatment impact, and it is usually easier to analyze the representatives of the sample and generalize the results. As stated by Lakens (2022), justifying the sample size is important in designing an empirical study. The main objective of this justification is to explain how the obtained data is likely to yield useful information given the researcher's inferential goals. Moreover, the study's findings are targeted to be presented at local, national, and international research conferences for a broader purview. Also, for future researchers to access the present study, this is targeted to be published in internationally recognized double-blind peer-reviewed journals.

Instrument

There were three sets of survey questionnaires used to gather data from the respondents of the study. The first set of questionnaires was the Regulation of Learning Questionnaire by (Hadwin et al., 2017). The second instrument was the Teaching Practices designed by Hong et al. (2006). Lastly, the third instrument was the Study Skills adjusted from Sabbah (2016). To meet the requirements of validity of the research instrument, the researcher honored the fidelity of undergoing the research tool from face validity. As accentuated by Creswell and Creswell (2018), validity explains how well the collected data covers the actual area of investigation. In this account, the survey questionnaire was forwarded to a panel of experts in questionnaire construction for a modification process to fit the culture of the respondents. In this study, a four-point Likert scale was used for it is one of the most commonly used scales.

Procedure

At the outset, the researchers conceptualized the research framework. Upon approval, the adapted survey questionnaires were organized and submitted to a panel of examiners for face validation purposes. In addition, the researcher asked permission from the Principal of the Senior High School Department to conduct the present study. More so, the researcher personally distributed the tool to the respondents and explained to them the rationale behind the research problems. Hereafter, the researcher retrieved the survey questionnaire after the respondents answered all the items indicated in the research tools. Afterward, tabulation of the data was done and they were subjected to statistical treatment. Henceforward, statistical results were analyzed meticulously and interpreted with professional prudence to establish meaningful findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Results and Discussion

This section introduces the data and findings of the study based on the elicited responses of the SHS students on the self-regulated learning promotion, teaching practices of SHS teachers, and study skills of SHS students.

Table 1. *Level of Self-Regulated Learning Promotion of SHS Students*

	<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	thinking about what really needs to be learned before beginning a task	3.44	0.628	Very High
2.	setting goals to help manage study time	3.30	0.796	Very High
3.	making sure to keep up with weekly readings and assignments	3.09	0.785	High
4.	thinking of alternative ways of solving a problem and choosing the best one	3.11	0.782	High
5.	being aware of what strategies to use when studying	3.08	0.780	High
6.	using strategies that have worked in the past	3.16	0.761	High
7.	thinking about what has been learned after finish studying	3.16	0.723	High
8.	changing strategies when not making progress while learning	3.16	0.761	High
9.	finding a comfortable place to study	3.48	0.775	Very High
10.	focusing on schoolwork when facing with distractions	2.83	0.994	High
11.	taking down notes on readings, PowerPoints, or video lectures	3.14	0.883	High
12.	asking how well the goals are accomplished once it is finished	3.09	0.819	High
13.	submitting all assignments on time	3.13	0.836	High
14.	creating a study schedule	2.75	1.006	High
15.	learning to use a new type of technology efficiently	3.12	0.798	High
16.	overcoming technical difficulties	3.07	0.798	High
17.	using the library's online resources efficiently	2.90	0.928	High
18.	searching the internet to find the answer to a course-related question	3.40	0.804	Very High
19.	searching the online course materials	3.23	0.797	High
20.	managing to keep working until it is finished	3.24	0.753	High
	Overall	3.14	0.446	High

The high rating of the self-regulated learning promotion denotes that this variable is frequently manifested, congruent to the affirmations of Pandey et al. (2018) that in psychological concept, self-regulation involves different skills such as managing emotions, maintaining positive relationships, avoiding inappropriate or aggressive behaviors, and being capable of independent learning. This means that students can learn by themselves using their thoughts and actions to reach their learning goals. In addition, Vosniadou (2020) stated that self-regulated learning plays a very important role in the students' accomplishments.

In this variable, the line item that has the highest mean rating that was given by the respondents is - finding a comfortable place to study. This means that a conducive place is much sought-after in independent learning, a component of SRL. This result supports the idea of Belbase et al. (2018) who argued that the quality of the students' learning depends on their home environment, school setting, and classroom atmosphere. Additionally, students should have a comfortable place where they can work alone with their peers (Valtonen et al., 2020). With that, schools need to set the example for creating a welcoming and healthy atmosphere as well as compassionate and well-mannered students (Kamil et al., 2020).

The item with the lowest mean which is focusing on schoolwork when facing distractions is also described as high. In the study of Xu et al. (2022), it was suggested that improving the learning surroundings for students could have advantages beyond their academic performance and overall well-being. Through self-regulated learning, learners proactively engage their thoughts, emotions, and actions to achieve their individual goals (Theobald, 2021). Moreover, learners identify their requirements, set goals, research appropriate learning materials, and evaluate their own learning experiences (Tosuncuoğlu, 2019).

The very high rating of the respondents on the teaching practices of SHS teachers in table 2 indicates that this variable is always manifested. Aligning with the assertions of Vosniadou (2020), teachers should recognize that students' academic achievements are connected to how students engage in the learning process which means that teachers' actions and communication affect the students. Teachers' communication and the way they communicate can shape the students' enthusiasm and outlook, contributing to a positive and engaging environment (Duță et al., 2015). Without assistance and directions from a teacher, the capacity to control students' learning process is a critical skill for achieving personal goals for education (Cicchinelli et al., 2018).

The very high level of teaching practices of SHS teachers is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on - using different approaches. The teaching-learning process is the transformation of knowledge from instructors to learners (Munna & Kalam, 2021). Implementing pedagogical approaches fosters student engagement, improves critical and creative thinking skills, decreases apathy, and actively participates in their learning experience (Santos et al., 2019). Additionally, alternative teaching approaches serve as valuable guidelines for educators in selecting appropriate teaching methods throughout the teaching-learning process (Mohd Izwan et al., 2023).

The item with the lowest mean which is - coping with classroom context appropriately is described as high. According to the study of Peterson et al. (2018), pedagogy offers structures for the multitude of decisions educators must make regarding their methods of instruction.

Additionally, a better understanding of innovative pedagogies is required for educators to address educational challenges and improve their professional competencies (Paniagua & Istance, 2018). Overall, it is not only for acquiring knowledge but also for fostering students' skills in character development (Malikovna, 2022).

Table 2. *Level of Teaching Practices of SHS Teachers*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. knowing the content to teach	3.49	0.538	Very High
explaining clearly the content of the subject	3.37	0.619	Very High
3. knowing how theories or principles of the subject have been developed	3.17	0.800	High
4. selecting appropriate content for students	3.22	0.806	High
5. knowing the answers to questions that the students ask about the subject.	3.25	0.747	High
6. explaining the impact of the subject matter on society	3.33	0.768	Very High
7. making the students clearly understand the objectives of the subject	3.25	0.768	High
8. providing an appropriate interaction or a good atmosphere	3.26	0.798	Very High
9. paying attention to students' reactions during class and adjusting his/her teaching	3.38	0.742	Very High
10. creating a classroom circumstance to promote students' interest in learning	3.25	0.771	High
11. preparing additional teaching materials	3.17	0.752	High
12. coping with classroom context appropriately	3.15	0.780	High
13. using appropriate examples to explain concepts related to the subject matter	3.27	0.812	Very High
14. using familiar analogies to explain concepts of subject matter	3.23	0.820	High
15. using teaching methods that keep students interested in the subject.	3.25	0.722	High
16. providing opportunities for students to express their views during class.	3.31	0.739	Very High
using demonstrations to help explain the main concept	3.32	0.765	Very High
18. being aware of the knowledge that the students have before they start the class	3.36	0.751	Very High
19. using multimedia or technology (e.g. PowerPoint) to express the concept of the subject	3.37	0.776	Very High
20. using different approaches (questions, discussion, etc.) to find out whether students understand	3.54	0.686	Very High
Overall	3.30	0.447	Very High

The high rating of the respondents on the study skills in table 3 denotes that this variable is frequently manifested. This is aligned with the assertions of Jafari et al. (2019) that effective study habits are the most important indicator of academic success and have a unique bearing on students' academic accomplishments. Numerous elements contribute to the quality of student learning (Belbase et al., 2018). Additionally, Salcedo-Relucio (2019) stated that it is also important that parents support their children by creating a conducive study environment, providing necessary studying materials, and actively assisting them.

In this variable, the item that has the highest mean rating given by the students is - studying in a place to concentrate. Students' views toward school and the classroom environment can affect how well they adjust to the school setting (Walker & Graham, 2019).

Table 3. *Level of Study Skills of Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. reading textbooks, slides, or podcasts	3.27	0.812	Very High
2. studying in a place to concentrate	3.47	0.786	Very High
3. making charts, diagrams, or tables to help organize course material	3.10	0.834	High
4. studying new course material thoroughly and skim it to see how it is organized	3.09	0.819	High
5. reviewing assignments	3.19	0.904	High
6. creating own questions	2.97	0.981	High
7. reviewing class notes and finding the most important ideas	3.26	0.798	Very High
8. relating the concept to prior knowledge	3.26	0.798	Very High
9. writing brief summaries of the main ideas from the readings and class notes	3.17	0.811	High
10. determining which concepts are not understood well	3.33	0.743	Very High
11. creating a study schedule	2.93	1.011	High
12. changing the way in reading the concept if it is difficult to understand	3.13	0.731	High
13. explaining the concept to a classmate or friend because it helps to understand better	3.22	0.783	High
14. practicing questions from sample exams or quizzes	3.14	0.903	High
15. practicing writing code on paper to get used to it in the exam	2.94	0.891	High
16. memorizing keywords and mnemonics	3.38	0.742	Very High
17. attend exam review sessions	3.26	0.798	Very High
18. applying course readings in other class activities such as lecture and discussion	3.25	0.771	High
19. trying to study without help from anyone	3.38	0.742	Very High
20. using external sources (ex: search online, another book, course material from another source)	3.37	0.788	Very High
Overall	3.21	0.501	High

The learning environment greatly affects the students' academic achievement and if it is accessible and utilizable, it will guarantee effective teaching and learning process (Madudili, 2024). Improving the learning environment for the students not just increases their academic performance but also their overall well-being (Xu et al., 2022).

The item with the lowest mean rating is - creating a study schedule which is described as high. Students grapple with the challenge of harmonizing their study commitments with the demands of their daily lives (Adams & Blair, 2019). In the study by Agormedah et al. (2021), it highlighted the importance of management since it serves as a crucial tool not only fostering improved academic performance but also a key factor in alleviating the burdens of depression and safety and stress that students often encounter. Overall, Jafari et al. (2019) stated that good study skills are highly significant in predicting students' academic success and are the best indicator of academic performance.

Table 4. *Correlation Between Variables*

Variables	Study Skills		
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H0
Self-Regulated Learning Promotion	.813	.000	Rejected
Teaching Practices of SHS Teachers	.651	.000	Rejected

Self-regulated learning promotion is related to study skills because the null hypothesis was rejected. The result was affirmed by the study of Pandey et al. (2018) that self-regulation includes a number of crucial skills, including emotional control, maintaining interpersonal connections refraining from inappropriate behaviors, and the capacity of self-directed learning. This was also anchored on the Self-Determination Theory of Ryan and Deci (2017) that personal and contextual factors play a significant role in shaping human behaviors. With that, students take responsibility for their education, set objectives, monitor their progress, and modify their strategies to achieve better in school.

The teaching practices of SHS teachers are related to study skills as well since the null hypothesis was rejected. The result was affirmed by the study of Santos et al. (2019) that implementing innovative teaching methods increases students' engagement, enhances critical and creative thinking skills, diminishes apathy, and allows students to actively participate in the learning process. It is also found in the ASSURE model that was developed by Heinrich and Molenda in 1990 which means Analyze learners, State objectives, Utilize materials, Require learner performance, and Evaluate the teaching and learning process is based upon constructivism and is also a component of the qualities of the pupil, whose recognition is made in the initial phase of the procedure (Gonzalez & Quiroz 2019). The ASSURE model is based on constructivism and part of the characteristics of the student, whose identification is made in the first stage of the process which is to analyze learners by identifying their expectations, goals, preferences, and needs (Gonzalez & Quiroz, 2019). Moreover, innovative teaching methods not only enrich the learning experience but also empower students with the study skills necessary to thrive in their academic pursuits.

Table 5. *Influence of Self-Regulated Learning Promotion and Teaching Practices of SHS Teachers on the Study Skills*

Independent Variables	Study Skills				
	F-value	R2	β Coefficient	t-value	p-value
Self-Regulated Learning Promotion	114.655	.676	.767	9.312	.000
Teaching Practices of SHS Teachers			.217	2.640	.010

Self-regulated learning promotion influences the study skills of SHS students. In line with the concept of Tosuncuoğlu (2019), it was stated that when learners exercise self-regulation, they identify their requirements, set goals, research appropriate learning materials, and evaluate their own learning experiences. Self-regulation plays a pivotal role in shaping study skills by instilling habits of goal setting, time management, active learning, and self-monitoring. By integrating these skills into the students' study habits, learners become more efficient, effective, and autonomous in their pursuit of academic excellence.

The teaching practices of SHS teachers also influence the study skills of SHS students. in accordance with the concept of Cicchinelli et al. (2018), it was stated that without assistance and direction from a teacher, the capacity to control one's learning process is a critical skill to achieve personal goals for education. Providing constructive feedback, encouraging self-reflection, and offering guidance on effective study strategies to empower students in developing their self-regulation and metacognitive skills. Ultimately, the teaching practices of SHS teachers directly influence students' acquisition and refinement of study skills, laying the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning.

Conclusions

The objectives, results, and findings of the study were the baseline in the formulation of the following conclusions. The study highlights the significant role of self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices in shaping the study skills of SHS students. The level of self-regulated learning promotion of SHS students is high. It means that self-regulated learning promotion is frequently manifested. Moreover, the level of teaching practices of SHS teachers is very high. It means that the teaching practices of SHS teachers are always manifested. In addition, the level of study skills of the SHS students has reached the descriptive level which is high, thus, it is also frequently manifested. In general, self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers have a significant

relationship with the study skills of students.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were crafted for consideration of the beneficiaries of this study:

To elevate the high level of self-regulated learning promotion, SHS teachers may integrate activities such as sessions where SHS students set goals, create reflection journals, and identify challenges. They may also have peer teaching assignments to reinforce understanding and communication skills, and retrieval practice through self-quiz to enhance memory retention.

To sustain the very high level of teaching practices of SHS teachers, they may continue to collaborate with other SHS teachers to share best practices and innovative teaching strategies, regularly assess student needs and adjust learning approaches when needed, provide timely and constructive feedback to students, and also foster a supportive learning environment that encourages active participation and critical thinking.

To improve the high level of study skills among senior high school students, the SHS faculty and staff may conduct seminars and workshops to expose students to different study techniques from renowned speakers. The SHS teachers may also employ active learning techniques such as creating a concept map and doing self-quiz, participating in group study, and prioritizing self-care practices to maintain focus and well-being.

Since self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers are related to the study skills of SHS students, SHS teachers may integrate clear instructions on effective study strategies and time management techniques into their curriculum and provide feedback and opportunities for the students to take ownership of their learning process.

The significant influence of self-regulated learning promotion and teaching practices of SHS teachers on the study skills suggests that integrating professional development programs focused on enhancing teachers' knowledge and skills in fostering self-regulated learning can benefit student outcomes. By providing support and resources for teachers, this can lead to more effective learning environments and improved academic performance among senior high school students and the academic community as a whole.

The present study used a quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational approach with two independent variables and one dependent variable. Future researchers may conduct a qualitative study to obtain a rich depth of information about self-regulated learning promotion, teaching practices of SHS teachers, and study skills of students. This method allows the study to grasp people's experiences and perspectives. Additionally, they may explore a mixed methods design focusing on an explanatory sequential approach so they may utilize the findings of this study to be the basis of the interview guide for the qualitative part of the research design.

References

- Adams, R. V., & Blair, E. (2019). Impact of time management behaviors on undergraduate engineering students' performance. *SAGE Open*, 9(1), 215824401882450. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018824506>
- Agormedah, E. K., Britwum, F., Amoah, S., Acheampong, H. Y., Adjei, E., & Nyamekye, F. (2021). Assessment of time management practices and students' academic achievement: The moderating role of gender. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v8i4p171>
- Belbase, S., Horemans, H., Makhija, H., & Munster, J. K. (2018). Book review: Teach students how to learn: Strategies you can incorporate into any course to improve student metacognition, study skills, and motivation. *Learning & Teaching in Higher Education: Gulf Perspectives*, 15(2), 83–84. <https://doi.org/10.18538/lthe.v15.n2.292>
- Biau, D., Kernéis, S., & Porcher, R. (2008). Statistics in brief: The importance of sample Size in the planning and interpretation of medical research. *Clinical orthopaedics and related research*, 466, 2282-8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11999-008-0346-9>
- Bibi, A., Naseer, N., & Habib, Z. (2020). Study habits of students and academic achievement: A correlational study. *Glob. Educ. Stud. Rev*, 5, 114-122.
- Burden, P. R. (2020). Classroom management: Creating a successful K-12 learning community. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA81955331>
- Burmeister, E., & Aitken, L. M. (2012). Sample size: How many is enough? *Australian Critical Care*, 25(4), 271–274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aucc.2012.07.002>
- Cicchinelli, A., Veas, E., Pardo, A., Pammer-Schindler, V., Fessler, A., Barreiros, C., & Lindstädt, S. (2018). Finding traces of self-regulated learning in activity streams. *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Learning Analytics*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3170358.3170381>
- Creswell, J., & Creswell, D. (2018). *Research design qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE. https://spada.uns.ac.id/pluginfile.php/510378/mod_resource/content/1/creswell.pdf
- Duță, N., Pânișoară, G., & Pânișoară, I. (2015). The effective communication in teaching. diagnostic study regarding the academic learning motivation to students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 186, 1007–1012.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.064>

García-Martínez, I., Batanero, J. M. F., Sanchíz, D. C., & De La Rosa, A. L. (2019). Using mobile devices for improving learning outcomes and teachers' professionalization. *Sustainability*, 11(24), 6917. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11246917>

Gettinger, M., & Seibert, J. K. (2019). Contributions of study skills to academic competence. *School Psychology Review*, 31(3), 350–365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2002.12086160>

Göğüş, A., & Ertek, G. (2020). A scoring approach for the assessment of study skills and learning styles. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 10(10), 715–722. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2020.10.10.1448>

Gonzalez, L. F., & Quiroz, V. G. (2019). Instructional design in online education: A systemic approach. *European Journal of Education*, 2(3), 64. <https://doi.org/10.26417/ejed.v2i3.p64-7>

Hadwin, Allyson & Järvelä, Sanna & Miller, Mariel. (2017). Self-regulation, co-regulation and shared regulation in collaborative learning environments.

Hong, E., Greene, M. T., & Higgins, K. (2006). Instructional practices of teachers in general education classrooms and gifted resource rooms: Development and validation of the instructional practice questionnaire. *Gifted Child Quarterly*, 50(2), 91-103. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001698620605000202>

Jafari, H., Aghaei, A., & Khatony, A. (2019). Relationship between study habits and academic achievement in students of medical sciences in Kermanshah-Iran. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, Volume 10, 637–643. <https://doi.org/10.2147/amep.s208874>

Jansen, R. S., Van Leeuwen, A., Janssen, J., Jak, S., & Kester, L. (2019). Self-regulated learning partially mediates the effect of self-regulated learning interventions on achievement in higher education: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 28, 100292. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2019.100292>

Kamil, P. A., Putri, E. I. K., Ridha, S., Utaya, S., Sumarmi, S., & Utomo, D. H. (2020). Promoting environmental literacy through a green project: A case study at Adiwiyata School in Banda Aceh City. *IOP Conference Series. Earth and Environmental Science*, 485(1), 012035. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/485/1/012035>

Lakens, Daniël. (2022). Sample size justification. *Collabra: Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1525/collabra.33267>.

Madudili, C. G. (2024). Conducive learning environment: A critical necessity for students' academic achievement in Nigeria. *Madudili | Journal of Science Education & Allied Disciplines*. <https://www.josead.com/index.php/JOSEAD/article/view/11/11>

Maican, M., & Cocoradă, E. (2021). Online foreign language learning in higher education and its correlates during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Maleki, A., Picolo, C., & Verrett, J. (2018). Effect of a mini-lesson on self-regulated learning on students' learning. *Proceedings of the Canadian Engineering Education Association (CEEA)*. <https://doi.org/10.24908/pceea.v0i0.13023>

Malgapo, C. R. T., & Ancheta, C. M. D. (2020). Pedagogical approaches and techniques of non-education graduates teaching general mathematics in the senior high school. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 6(11). <http://www.journal-repository.theshillonga.com/index.php/ijaems/article/view/2703>

Malikovna, K. R. (2022). Types of interactive methods in teaching English to students. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* -. <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/2641>

Mejeh, M., & Held, T. (2022). Understanding the development of self-regulated learning: An intervention study to promote self-regulated learning in vocational schools. *Vocations and Learning*, 15(3), 531–568. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-022-09298-4>

Mertler, Craig. (2018). *Introduction to educational research*. SAGE Publications <https://edge.sagepub.com/mertler2e>

Mohd Izwan, S., Guntur, Yin, T. T., & Mustafa, L. M. (2023). Alternative pedagogy approaches in physical education and health education. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice; West Palm Beach*, 23(6), 47–54. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/alternative-pedagogy-approaches-physical/docview/2804344448/se-2>

Munna, A. S., & Kalam, A. (2021). Teaching and learning process to enhance teaching effectiveness: Literature review. *IJHI (International Journal of Humanities and Innovation)*, 4

Palbusa, M. Y., Jr. (2021). Senior high school as critical pedagogy. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1351547>

Pandey, A., Hale, D. R., Das, S., Goddings, A., Blakemore, S. J., & Viner, R. (2018). Effectiveness of universal self-regulation-based interventions in children and adolescents. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 172(6), 566. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2018.0232>

Paniagua, A., & Istance, D. (2018). Teachers as designers of learning environments: The importance of innovative pedagogies. In

Educational research and innovation. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264085374-en>

Patino, C. M., & Ferreira, J. C. (2018). Inclusion and exclusion criteria in research studies: definitions and why they matter. *Jornal Brasileiro De Pneumologia*, 44(2), 84. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s1806-37562018000000088>

Peterson, A., Dumont, H., Lafuente, M., & Law, N. (2018). Understanding innovative pedagogies. OECD Education Working Papers. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9f843a6e-e>

Sabbah, Sabah. (2016). The effect of study habits on english language achievement. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 10.2139/ssrn.2898626.

Salcedo-Relucio, M. A. (2019). Factors affecting the study habits of grade eleven students in one national high school in Pangasinan, Philippines. *Southeast Asian Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 89-97.

Santos, J. O., Figueiredo, A. S., & Vieira, M. (2019). Innovative pedagogical practices in higher education: An integrative literature review. *Nurse Education Today*, 72, 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2018.10.003>

Saunders, M., Lewis, P., Thornhill, A., & Bristow, A. (2019). Research methods for business students chapter 4: Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330760964>

Segolsson, M., & Hirsh, Å. (2019). How skilled teachers enable success in their teaching with respect to inclusion and knowledge development: A qualitative study based on teachers' experiences of successful teaching. *International Journal of Teaching and Education*, VII(2). <https://doi.org/10.20472/te.2019.7.2.004>

Suciu, A. I., & MĂȚĂ, L. (2011). Pedagogical competencies - The key to efficient education. *International Online Journal Education Sciences*. http://www.iojes.net/userfiles/Article/IOJES_402.pdf

Taherdoost, H. (2016). Sampling methods in research methodology; How to choose a sampling technique for research. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3205035>

Theobald, M. (2021). Self-regulated learning training programs enhance university students' academic performance, self-regulated learning strategies, and motivation: A meta-analysis. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 66, 101976. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2021.101976>

Tosuncuoğlu, İ. (2019). The interconnection of motivation and self-regulated learning among university-level EFL students. *English Language Teaching*, 12(4), 105. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v12n4p105>

Valtonen, T., Leppänen, U., Hyypiä, M., Kokko, A., Manninen, J., Vartiainen, H., Sointu, E., & Hirsto, L. (2020). Learning environments preferred by university students: A shift toward informal and flexible learning environments. *Learning Environments Research*, 24(3), 371–388. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-020-09339-6>

Viberg, O., Khalil, M., & Baars, M. (2020). Self-regulated learning and learning analytics in online learning environments. In the 10th International Conference on Learning Analytics & Knowledge (LAK'20). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3375462.3375483>

Vosniadou, S. (2020). Bridging secondary and higher education: The importance of self-regulated learning. *European Review*, 28(S1), S94–S103. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1062798720000939>

Walker, S., & Graham, L. J. (2019). At risk students and teacher-student relationships: Student characteristics, attitudes to school and classroom climate. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 25(8), 896–913. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1588925>

Xu, X., Schönrock-Adema, J., Jaarsma, A., Duvivier, R., & Bos, N. (2022). A conducive learning environment in international higher education: A systematic review of research on students' perspectives. *Educational Research Review*, 37, 100474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2022.100474>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Phoebe P. Escosar

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines

Louie Jay R. Caloc

St. John Paul II College of Davao – Philippines